

USING “PROGRAM SHAPING” AND ALGORITHMIC SKELETONS TO PARALLELISE AN EVOLUTIONARY MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM IN ERLANG

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Abstract. This paper considers how to use *program shaping* and *algorithmic skeletons* to parallelise a multi-agent system that is written in Erlang. *Program shaping* is the process of transforming a program to better enable the introduction of parallelism. Whilst *algorithmic skeletons* abstract away the low-level aspects of parallel programming that often plague traditional techniques, it is not always easy to introduce them into an arbitrary program, especially one that has not been written with parallelism in mind. Amongst other issues, data may not always be in a compatible format, function calls may need to be replicated to support alternative uses, side-effects may need to be isolated, or there may be dependencies between functions and data that obstruct the introduction of parallelism. *Program shaping* can be used to transform such code to a form that allows skeletons to be more easily introduced. In this paper, we present a series of generic *program shaping* rewrite rules, provide their implementation as *refactorings*, and show how they can be used to parallelise an Evolutionary Multi-Agent System (MAS) written in Erlang. We show that we can significantly speed up this application, obtaining *super-linear speedups* of over 70× the original sequential performance on a 64-core shared-memory machine.

1 INTRODUCTION

Parallel processors are now ubiquitous. Consequently, parallel programming is an increasingly necessary skill for the average programmer. Traditional parallelisation techniques consist of low-level primitives and libraries that require the programmer to manually introduce and manage detailed parallelism constructs, e.g. threads, communication, locking, and synchronisation. This results in a process which is often tedious, difficult, and error-prone [25]. In response, a number of approaches have been devised that aim to simplify the parallelisation process (e.g. [15, 37, 38, 39, 46]). While these approaches take different approaches, they all abstract away low-level parallel mechanics, which is a common source of error. Although beneficial, these abstractions only serve to address one specific problem, however: that the interfaces to parallel primitives and libraries are often too low-level. Other aspects of parallelism, such as which part(s) of a program should be parallelised [1] or which parallel configuration gives the best performance gains [29], must be similarly addressed. One common and non-trivial aspect of parallelisation, which has so far received little attention, is how best to restructure code to enable the introduction of parallelism. This may involve e.g. the detection and breaking of inter-task dependencies, the detection of side-effects that inhibit parallelism, changing data representations to avoid excessive memory use, and/or avoiding scheduler inefficiencies. This requires extensive knowledge of the program code, the language used, and parallelism itself. The difficulty of this task makes it a significant stage of the parallelisation process. This restructuring stage is a form of *program shaping*, which we define to be *a series of intentional changes to source code that contribute towards some goal*.

At present, program shaping is generally a manual, *ad hoc*, and error-prone process. This paper investigates how to increase the automation of the program shaping task, using *refactoring*. A *refactoring* [21] is a conditional, source-to-source program transformation that maintains functional correctness. While manual refactorings are possible, refactoring tools can perform transformations both automatically and *safely*. Such tools exist for a wide range of languages, and are often integrated with popular editors [40]. In the functional programming community, well-known examples include Wrangler [35] and RefactorErl [26] for Erlang, and Hare for Haskell [36]. Recent work has demonstrated that refactoring can be used to automate the introduction of parallelism [2]. This paper extends that work to program shaping, demonstrating how program shaping can be applied to a large-scale evolutionary multi-agent system (EMAS) written in Erlang. “Evolution” means that agents are able to *reproduce* (generate new agents), which is a kind of cooperative interaction, and may *die* (be eliminated from the system), which is the result of competition (selection). The idea of an Evolutionary Multi-agent System was first introduced by Cetnarowicz in 1996 [13]. Since then it has been implemented a number of times (e.g., [8, 18]), analysed [9], and extended [43, 7]. EMAS have turned out to be an efficient paradigm for solving a variety of complex optimisation problems [49, 10].

Evolutionary processes are by nature decentralised and therefore evolutionary processes may be easily introduced in a multi-agent system at a population level. In this paper, we demonstrate how such an evolutionary MAS, built in Erlang, might be semi-automatically restructured and parallelised using new automated refactoring techniques for program shaping. We provide a description of the refactorings used below, and demonstrate that, in combination with the use of algorithmic skeletons, we can achieve excellent performance gains (in the best case, over 70×, on a 64-core multicore system).

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Algorithmic Skeletons

Algorithmic skeletons abstract commonly-used patterns of parallel computation, communication, and interaction [15] into parameterised templates. There has been a long-standing connection between the skeletons community and the functional programming community. In the functional world, skeletons are effectively higher-order functions that can be instantiated with specific user code to give some concrete parallel behaviour. For example, we might define a *parallel map* skeleton, whose functionality is identical to a standard *map* function, but which creates a number of processes (*worker processes*) to execute each element of the map in parallel. A recent survey of algorithmic skeleton approaches can be found at [23]. Using a skeleton approach allows the programmer to adopt a top-down *structured* approach to parallel programming, where skeletons are composed to give the overall parallel structure of the program. This gives a flexible semi-implicit approach, where the parallelism is exposed to the programmer only through the choice of skeleton and perhaps through some specific behavioural parameters (e.g. the number of parallel processes to be created, or how elements of the parallel list are to be grouped to reduce communication costs). Details such as communication, task creation, task or data migration, scheduling etc. are embedded within the skeleton implementation, which may be tailored to a specific architecture or class of architectures. This offers an improved level of portability over the typical low-level approaches. However, it will still be necessary to tune behavioural parameters in particular cases, and it may even be necessary to alter the parallel structure to deal with alternative hardware architectures (especially where an application targets different classes of architecture).

2.1.1 SKEL

The SKEL [2] library defines a small set of classical skeletons for Erlang. Each skeleton operates over a stream of input values, producing a corresponding stream of results. Because each skeleton is defined as a streaming operation, they can be freely substituted provided they have equivalent types. The same property also

Fig. 1. A Task Farm Skeleton

allows simple composition and nesting of skeletons. This paper will consider the following subset of the SKEL skeletons:

- **func** is a simple wrapper skeleton that encapsulates a function, $f : a \rightarrow b$, as a skeleton, enabling the use of the function within SKEL.
- **pipe** models a parallel pipeline over a sequence of skeletons s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n as a skeleton, enabling parallel composition of skeletons.
- **farm** models a task farm (see Fig. 1) with n workers, whose operation is the skeleton s .
- **feedback** models a feedback skeleton that allows inputs to be applied to some skeleton s repeatedly until some condition c is met.

2.2 Refactoring

Refactoring is the process of changing the internal structure of a program, while preserving its (functional) behaviour. In contrast to general program transformations, refactoring focuses on purely structural changes rather than on changes to program functionality, and it is generally applied semi-automatically, i.e. under programmer direction. This allows programmer knowledge about e.g. safety properties to be exploited, and so permits a wider range of possible transformation than a fully automatic approach. Refactoring has many advantages over traditional transformation and fully automated approaches, including (but not limited to):

Fig. 2. Wrangler’s menu in Emacs

- Refactoring is aimed at improving the design of software. As programmers change software to meet new requirements, so the code loses structure; regular refactoring helps tidy up the code to retain a good structure.
- Refactoring makes software easier to understand. Programmers often write software without considering future developers. Refactoring can enable the code to better communicate its purpose.
- Refactoring encourages code reuse by removing duplicated code [5].
- Refactoring helps the programmer to program faster and more effectively by encouraging good program design.
- Refactoring helps the programmer to reduce bugs. As refactorings typically generate code automatically, it is easy to guarantee that this code is safe and correct [45].

The term “refactoring” was first introduced by Opdyke in his 1992 PhD thesis [41], but the concept goes back at least to Darlington and Burstall’s 1977 *fold/unfold* transformation system [6], which aimed to improve code maintainability by transforming Algol-style recursive loops into a pattern-matching style commonly used today. Historically, most refactoring was performed manually with the help of text editor “search and replace” facilities. However, in the last couple of decades, a diverse range of refactoring tools have become available for various programming languages, that aid the programmer by offering a selection of automatic refactorings. For example, the most recent release of the IntelliJ IDEA refactoring supports 35 distinct refactorings for Java [19]. Typical refactorings include *variable renaming* (changing all instances of a variable that are in scope to a new name), *parameter adding* (introducing a new parameter to a function definition and updating all relevant calls to that function with a placeholder), *function extraction* (lifting a selected block of code into its own function) and *function inlining*.

2.2.1 Wrangler

While the refactoring community has produced a great deal of work for the object-oriented paradigm [16], the concept can be applied to a wide range of programming styles and approaches, including functional programming. Indeed, Darlington and Burstall’s transformation system for recursive functions produces code that would not be out of place in modern functional programs [6]. Li et al. have since produced the HaRe [36] and Wrangler [35] refactoring tools for Haskell and Erlang respectively. Both tools are implemented in their respective languages, and offer a number of standard refactorings. Wrangler is implemented in Erlang and is integrated into both Emacs (Fig. 2) and Eclipse. In this paper, we exploit a recent Wrangler extension which allows refactorings to be expressed as AST traversal strategies in terms of their pre-conditions and transformation rules. The extension comes in two parts: a user-level language for describing the refactorings themselves [33]; plus a Domain-Specific Language (DSL) to compose the refactorings [33].

2.3 Evolutionary Multi-Agent System

A common approach to problem solving is to decompose that problem into smaller tasks, to solve each (sub)task independently, and to subsequently combine the solutions to produce an overall solution. This approach to problem solving lends itself well to parallel and distributed computing, where subtasks can be run independently on separate cores or machines. A typical example of this approach is the master-slave evolution model [12]. Multi-agent systems extend this approach by treating the processes that solve the tasks as intelligent, autonomous agents, with each agent capable of interacting with their environment and other agents. As their name implies, a multi-agent system (MAS) combines two or more of these autonomous agents, making them ideally suited for representing problems that have many solving methods, involve many perspectives, and/or may be solved by many entities [48]. One of the major application areas of multi-agent systems is large-scale computing [47]. Evolutionary multi-agent systems are a hybrid meta-heuristic which combines multi-agent systems with evolutionary algorithms. The idea consists of evolving a population of agents to improve their ability to solve a particular optimisation problem [11, 9].

In a multi-agent system, no global knowledge is available to individual agents. Agents should remain autonomous and no central authority should be needed. Therefore, in an evolutionary computing system, unlike traditional evolutionary algorithms, selective pressure needs to be decentralised. Using agent terminology, we can say that selective pressure is required to emerge from peer-to-peer interactions between agents instead of being globally-driven. In a basic algorithm, every agent is assigned a real-valued vector that represents a potential solution to the optimisation problem, together with the corresponding fitness measure. Emergent selective pressure is achieved by giving agents a single non-renewable resource called energy. Agents start with an initial amount of energy and meet randomly. If their energy is below a threshold, they fight by comparing their fitness – better agents

Fig. 3. EMAS structure and principle of work

take energy from worse ones. Otherwise, the agents reproduce and yield a new one – the genotype of the child is derived from its parents using variation operators and it also receives some energy from its parents. Since the total energy remains constant, the system is stable. However, the number of agents may vary and adapt to the difficulty of the problem (see Fig. 3). As in other evolutionary algorithms, agents can be split into separate populations. Such sub-populations, called islands, help preserve diversity by introducing allopatric speciation and can also execute in parallel. Information is exchanged between islands through agent migrations. It should be noted that the EMAS computing abilities have been formally proven correct by constructing a detailed Markov-chain based model and proving its ergodicity property [9]. This result shows that EMAS are a general optimisation tool.

While the problems that can be solved by both evolutionary and standard multi-agent systems are varied, the approach and design of the underlying systems is often standard. Recent work by Krzywicki et al. [31] has developed patterns to describe the operation of evolutionary and multi-agent systems, with an example implementation in Erlang. While this implementation was initially completely sequential, through the use of the program shaping techniques and methodology described below, we have now been able to parallelise it successfully to give an efficient and scalable parallel implementation.

3 REWRITE RULES

In this section, we define a series of program shaping refactorings. All the refactorings presented below can be described as semi-formal rewrite rules, operating over the abstract syntax tree (AST) of the source program. Each refactoring has a set of conditions that ensure that the transformation is valid, a description of the syntax to be transformed, and a description of the revised syntax following the successful transformation. Conditions are given as predicates to each rule. Each rewrite rule operates within an environment, γ , allowing access and reference to the current scope of the rewrite rule within the source program. This includes the set of all available functions, \mathbb{F} . The skeleton library, SKEL , and the skeletons it provides are denoted by the set \mathbb{S} .

$$\mathbb{S} = \{skel, \bar{f}, pipe, farm, farm', farm'', cluster, cluster', cluster''\}$$

For all rewrite rules, \mathbb{S} is assumed to be in scope. This denoted in each rule by extending γ :

$$\Gamma = \gamma \cup \mathbb{S}$$

We define a series of semantic equivalences to allow for more concise rewrite rules. Each equivalence is subject to a series of predicates under which it is valid, and is defined in the form:

$$\bar{s}, xs \in \Gamma, xs : list\ a \vdash skel(\bar{s}, xs) = \mathbf{skel} : do(\bar{s}, xs)$$

where \bar{s} represents any valid skeleton in \mathbb{S} , i.e. $\mathbb{S}/\{skel\}$; and xs evaluates to a list where all elements have the same type. Semantic equivalences have been defined for each skeleton in SKEL , given in Fig. 4. Using these semantic equivalences we can define rewrite rules for each refactoring. Due to space limitations, we define two of our refactorings in this format (*Extract Composition Function* and *Introduce Func*), giving textual descriptions of the others in Fig 5.

3.1 Extract Composition Function

The *Extract Composition Function* refactoring exposes sequential functionality that may later be used as part of a parallel pipeline. While it is possible to immediately introduce a skeleton over a list comprehension, e.g. via *Intro Farm*, such refactorings commonly assume that the list comprehension is the top-level command. Where the list comprehension is nested within a loop, or is just part of a solution, it can be advantageous to lift each part of the solution into atomic closures of sequential functionality which can later be arranged into an optimal configuration for parallelism.

γ	=	Program Environment
\mathbb{F}	=	Set of all functions in γ
\mathbb{L}	=	Set of all lists in γ
\mathbb{S}	=	$\{skel, \bar{f}, pipe, farm\}$
Γ	=	$\gamma \cup \mathbb{S}$
Γ	\vdash	\mathcal{F}
	=	F
		<code>fun ?MODULE :f/1</code>
		<code>fun(x) → ... end</code>
$\Gamma, xs \in \mathbb{L}$	\vdash	<code>skel(\bar{s}, xs)</code>
	=	<code>skel : do(\bar{s}, xs)</code>
Γ	\vdash	\bar{f}
	=	$\{\mathbf{func}, \mathcal{F}\}$
Γ	\vdash	<code>pipe($\bar{s}_1, \dots, \bar{s}_2$)</code>
	=	$\{\mathbf{pipe}, [\bar{s}_1, \dots, \bar{s}_n]\}$
Γ	\vdash	<code>farm(\bar{s}, n)</code>
	=	$\{\mathbf{farm}, \bar{s}, n\}$
Γ	\vdash	<code>map(\mathcal{F}, xs)</code>
	=	<code>lists : map(\mathcal{F}, xs)</code>

Fig. 4. Environment Definitions and Semantic Equivalences for Refactoring Notation

Refactoring	Description
<i>Compose Maps</i>	Lifts a series of map operations $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_{n-1}, m_n$ such that the input of m_i is the output of m_{i-1} where $1 < i < n$, into a single anonymous function composing the functions of the map operations respectively. The function is then assigned to some user-provided variable name.
<i>Intro Skel</i>	Given some skeleton configuration, introduces a call to the SKEL library over some map operation or list comprehension.
<i>Intro Feedback</i>	Transforms some map-equivalent recursive function containing a call to SKEL, such that the call to SKEL is updated with a feedback skeleton, removing the outer recursive call.

Fig. 5. Textual Overview of Refactorings

The general case is defined as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Gamma, F \notin \Gamma, \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{E}_x} &\vdash R = [\mathcal{E}_x \mid x \leftarrow xs] \\
&\mapsto F = \underset{\mathcal{E}_x}{fun}(x, \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{E}_x}) \rightarrow \\
&\quad end, \\
&\quad R = map(F, xs)
\end{aligned}$$

where F is a valid user-provided variable name; \mathcal{E}_X denotes a set of Erlang statements parameterised over x ; and $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{E}_x}$ denotes the set of non- x arguments required by \mathcal{E}_x . In the general case, the statements that form the output expression are wrapped in an anonymous function and parameterised according to the variable dependencies of \mathcal{E}_x . This function is assigned to a user-provided variable name. Only one input variable may be provided by the input set. The result is a two-statement closure containing the lifted output expression and a map operation which applies the original input to the newly-created function. The refactoring can be extended to special cases that account for e.g. specific forms of list comprehension. For example, one variant lifts and assigns multiple nested functions. Given the code:

```
R = [f(g(X)) || X <- Xs]
```

it is possible to lift f and g into their own functions, producing:

```
RG = fun(X) -> g(X) end,
RF = fun(X) -> f(X) end,
Q = lists:map(RG, Xs),
R = lists:map(RF, Q)
```

3.2 Introduce Func

Once atomic sequential closures have been identified, perhaps through *Extract Composition Function*, it is then necessary to wrap the closures in a **func** skeleton in order to enable their use in SKEL. *Introduce Func* is defined as follows:

$$\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{F} \mapsto \bar{f}$$

where, as defined in Fig. 4, \mathcal{F} denotes the multiple possible representations of an Erlang function whose arity is 1. \mathcal{F} will not be transformed if wrapping it into a **func** skeleton would lead to syntactic errors.

4 REFACTORING THE MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM

We demonstrate how program shaping can be used by illustrating its application to an example MAS. The MAS operates over a number of generations to find a solution. Each generation may be modelled as an iteration of a loop, with each member of the system’s population performing its own work within each iteration. Both the outer generational loop and the work performed within that loop are highly suitable for parallelisation. The code below has been slightly simplified for readability.

```

loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  Tag = fun(Island) ->
    [{
      mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(
        Agent, SP, Cf),
      Agent} || Agent <- Island]

  end,

  Groups = [mas_misc_util:group_by(Tag(I)) || I <- Islands],

  Migrants = [seq_migrate(lists:keyfind(migration, 1, Island), Nr)
    || {Island, Nr} <-
      lists:zip(Groups,
        lists:seq(
          1,
          length(Groups)))],

  NewGroups = [[mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(
    Activity,
    mas_sequential,
    SP,
    Cf) || Activity <- I]
    || I <- Groups],

  WithMigrants = append(
    lists:flatten(Migrants),
    NewGroups),

  NewIslands = [mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
    || I <- WithMigrants],

  case os:timestamp() < Time of
  true ->
    loop(NewIslands, Time, SP, Cf);
  false ->
    NewIslands
  end.

```

While this code seems to be a good candidate for parallelisation, it cannot be parallelised immediately, and so needs to be *shaped* first. We show how this code may be shaped using some standard refactorings, plus the new refactorings from Section 3. We give only the affected code for each stage of the transformation. Full listings showing each transformation stage can be found in Appendix A.

4.1 Stage 1

We start shaping `loop/4` by extracting functions from the list comprehensions that are assigned to `Tagged`, `Groups`, and `Migrants` using the *Extract Comprehension Function* refactoring. This gives the following definitions.

```

TagFun =
  fun (Agent) ->
    {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                   SP,
                                   Cf),
      Agent}
  end,
Tagged = lists:map(TagFun, Islands),

GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,
Groups = lists:map(GroupFun, Tagged),

MigrantFun =
  fun ({Island, Nr}) ->
    seq_migrate(lists:keyfind(migration,
                              1, Island),
                Nr)
  end,
Migrants = lists:map(MigrantFun,
                    lists:zip(Groups,
                              lists:seq(
                                1,
                                length(Groups)))),

```

4.2 Stage 2

To facilitate its eventual composition with `TagFun` and `GroupFun`, we inline the function `MigrantsFun` using the classical *Inline Method* refactoring.

```

MigrantFun =
  fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
    Destinations =
      [{mas_topology:getDestination(From),
        Agent} || Agent <-Agents],
    mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
    (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent
  end,
Migrants = lists:map(MigrantFun,
                    lists:zip(Groups,
                              lists:seq(
                                1,
                                length(Groups)))),

```

4.3 Stage 3

Since `MigrantsFun` can now be composed with `TagFun` and `GroupFun`, we compose these three functions using the *Compose Functions* refactoring.

```

TagFun =
  fun (Agent) ->
    {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                   SP,
                                   Cf),
     Agent}
  end,

GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,

MigrantFun =
  fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
    Destinations =
      [{mas_topology:getDestination(From),
        Agent} || Agent <-Agents],
    mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
    (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent
  end,

TGM = fun(Agents) ->
  Tagged = lists:map(TagFun, Agents),
  Migrants = lists:map(MigrantFun, Tagged),
  GroupFun(Migrants)
end,

TGMs = lists:map(TGM, Islands),

```

Here we note that the input to the list comprehension assigned to `NewGroups` has been changed according to the newly introduced composition. Similarly we also remove `WithMigrants` with the `Remove Statement` refactoring, which requires the input to the list comprehension assigned to `NewIslands` to be changed to `NewGroups`.

4.4 Stage 4

We next focus our attention on the list comprehensions assigned to `NewGroups` and `NewIslands` respectively, applying the *Extract Comprehension Function* refactoring to both.

```

NewGroupsFunInnerFun =
  fun (Activity) ->
    mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(Activity,
                                 mas_sequential,
                                 SP,
                                 Cf)
  end,

NewGroupsFun =
  fun (I) ->
    lists:map(NewGroupsFunInnerFun, I)
  end,

NewGroups = lists:map(NewGroupsFun, TGMs),

```

```

NewIslandsFun =
  fun (I) ->
    mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
  end,
NewIslands = lists:map(NewIslandsFun, NewGroups),

```

4.5 Stage 5

Having shaped our existing functions into a suitable form for parallelisation, we now proceed to introduce the structures to pass to SKEL. We start with the map operation which applies TGM to each element in `Islands`, transforming it using the *Intro Func* refactoring to introduce a `func` skeleton. We apply the same refactoring to the `NewGroupsInnerFun` expression. Continuing this process, we next apply the *Intro Farm* refactoring over the `NewGroupsFun` expression.

```

TGMs = {func, TGM},

Work =
  {func,
   fun (Activity) ->
     mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(Activity,
                                  mas_farm,
                                  SP,
                                  Cf)
   end},
Map = {farm, [Work], Cf#config.skel_workers},
NewGroups = lists:map(NewGroupsFun, TGMs),

Shuffle =
  fun (I) ->
    mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
  end,
NewIslands = lists:map(Shuffle, NewGroups),

```

In order to aid readability, we also rename `NewIslandsFun` to `Shuffle`.

4.6 Stage 6

We again apply the *Intro Func* refactoring, this time over the renamed `Shuffle` expression, completing all the skeletons that are required to introduce the SKEL invocation. We can then apply the *Intro Skel* refactoring over `NewIslands` and `NewGroups`.

```

Shuffle =
  {func,
   fun (I) ->
     mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
   end},

Pipe = {pipe, [TGMs, Map, Shuffle]},
NewIslands =
  [NewIsland ||
   {_, NewIsland} <- skel:do([Pipe], Islands)],

```

4.7 Stage 7

While `loop/4` is now parallel, the outer loop itself can also be folded into the SKEL invocation to improve efficiency. We do this by applying the *Intro Feedback Loop* refactoring over `loop/4` itself.

```
loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  EndTime =
    mas_misc_util:add_miliseconds(os:timestamp(), Time),

  TagFun =
    fun (Agent) ->
      {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                     SP,
                                     Cf), Agent}

    end,

  GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,

  MigrantFun =
    fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
      Destinations =
        [{mas_topology:getDestination(From),
          Agent} || Agent <-Agents],
      mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
      (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent

    end,

  TGM = tgm(TagFun, GroupFun, MigrantFun),
  TGMs = {func, TGM},

  Work = {func,
          fun (Activity) ->
            mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(
              Activity,
              mas_farm,
              SP,
              Cf)

          end},

  Map = {farm, [Work], Cf#config.skel_workers},

  Shuffle = {func,
            fun (I) ->
              mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))

            end},

  Pipe = {pipe, [TGMs, Map, Shuffle]},
  Constraint = fun (_) -> os:timestamp() < Time end,
  FinalIslands = skel:do([farm,
                          {{feedback, [Pipe], Constraint}},
                          Cf#config.skel_workers}],
                          [Islands]).
```

This completes the shaping and parallelisation process.

5 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The aim of the parallelisation process presented in this paper is to convert a given program into an efficient parallel version. In order to evaluate the efficiency of the refactored code we compare it to different manually-generated implementations of the same algorithm that do not use the SKEL parallel pattern library and that do not use our program shaping methods. Two different implementations of the EMAS have been created: concurrent and hybrid. The concurrent version follows Erlang good practice for writing concurrent code, which assumes that fine-grained processes are created for all the individual tasks in the system. Every agent is represented by a different process and all communication uses message-passing. Agent interactions are mediated by special processes, called “meeting arenas”. This version is not influenced by the target hardware architecture – hundreds of truly concurrent agents are created each second making the Erlang scheduler responsible for managing the mapping of processes to hardware. The implementation can successfully run on one core as well as on hundreds of cores.

The hybrid version has been designed and manually tuned to give the best possible performance for the EMAS algorithm. The number of individual evolutionary islands is equal to the number of cores. Each evolutionary island is internally computed sequentially, while different islands use different processes. This approach limits context switching and communication to the minimum that is required by the incidental operations of agent migrations between islands and the collection of results.

Two different optimisation benchmark problems have been compared: continuous and discrete. The continuous problem was the Rastrigin function [17], a continuous benchmarking function that is commonly used to compare evolutionary algorithms. This function is highly multi-modal with many local minima and one global minimum equal to 0 at $\vec{x} = 0$. We used a problem size (the dimension of the function) equal to 100, in a domain equal to the hypercube $[50, 50]^{100}$. As this is a continuous optimisation problem, real-valued encoding was used, with Cauchy mutations and continuous recombination as genetic operators. The Rastrigin function has a simple formulation and is easy to compute. Therefore, fitness function computation is relatively cheap and the computation to communication ratio is low. The discrete problem was Low Autocorrelation Binary Sequences (LABS) [22]. LABS is an NP-hard combinatorial problem with a very simple formulation that has many applications in telecommunication (synchronisation, pulse compression, satellite and space applications, digital signal processing, high-precision interplanetary radar measurements), meteorology (calibration of surface profile meteorology tools), physics (Ising spin glasses, configuration state analysis, statistical mechanics) and chemistry. The LABS problem has a very difficult search space and therefore the fitness function computation is far more complex than for the Rastrigin function, making the computation to communication ratio much higher.

Fig. 6. Speedup of the three versions of the agent-based evolutionary algorithm executing the Rastrigin function optimisation

We ran our simulations on the ZEUS supercomputer provided by the PL-Grid¹ infrastructure at ACC Cyfronet AGH². We used nodes with 4 AMD Opteron 6276 processors, with up to 64 cores and 1 GB of memory. On this architecture we executed each of the three versions of the EMAS algorithm on configurations with 1, 4, 8, 16, 32, 48 and 64 cores. Each run took approximately five minutes, during which time we recorded the overall number of reproductions per second. Each experiment has been repeated 10 times – the charts below present the mean value of all runs. Results showing system scalability during the Rastrigin function optimisation are given in Figure 6. The problem with the low computation to communication ratio clearly shows that the overhead of creating hundreds of processes and passing hundreds of messages every second can reduce the scalability of the algorithm. The concurrent version scales linearly up to 16 cores only, while both the hybrid and SKEL-based implementations scale linearly up to 48 cores. The hybrid version shows the best characteristics in this case, outperforming the SKEL-based version especially when 64 cores are used.

The system scalability results during the LABS problem optimisation are shown in figure 7. They clearly show that in for problems with a high computation to communication ratio, all three versions can scale linearly (or even super-linearly). The SKEL-based version is slightly superior to the other two implementations for larger numbers of cores. The super-linearity can be explained by the fact that we have used a task farm. As soon as results are computed, they will be returned, so increasing the system throughput.

Overall, our experiments confirm that the pattern-based approach for sequential code parallelisation is a valid one to use and that it can provide highly efficient

¹ <http://plgrid.pl/>

² <http://www.cyfronet.krakow.pl/>

Fig. 7. Speedup of the three versions of the agent-based evolutionary algorithm executing LABS problem optimisation

solutions. While highly tuned and dedicated solutions can give better results for particular problems, as a general-purpose tool the SKEL and program approach gives very good results for relatively low effort.

6 RELATED WORK

The study of parallelism has a long and active history; often demonstrating the difficulties associated with the style, and illustrating its core requirements [44]. Approaches designed to simplify its introduction and management are numerous and varied; examples include: futures [20], evaluation strategies [46], monads [38], and algorithmic skeletons [14]. Each approach is similar in that low-level parallel mechanics are hidden from the programmer, and that each have requirements for their introduction. These requirements are unlikely to be met without the need for program transformation, however.

As with parallelism, the study of program transformation is not a new area, with Partsch and Steinbrüggen describing early work in 1983 [42], and more recently by Mens in 2004 [40]. In the functional programming community, refactoring tools have been built for both Haskell and Erlang [32, 30].

Despite the work done for both algorithmic skeletons and program transformation, there have only been limited attempts at combining the two [25]. Some attempts include high-level pattern-based rewrites including extensions to Haskell’s refactoring tool HaRe [4], and similar, cost-directed refactorings for Wrangler [2]. These extensions are limited by the number of refactorings they include, and by their focus on the introduction and manipulation of skeleton library invocations. Transformations that allow the introduction of high-level parallel libraries remain a predominantly manual process.

In [2], we introduced a parallel refactoring methodology for programming Erlang programs, to facilitate the introduction of parallel skeletons. In [3] and [28], we presented parallel refactoring techniques for C++ programs. This paper goes beyond that work in introducing novel program shaping rather than pure skeleton introduction. As a technique, program shaping is relatively new and untouched by both skeletons and refactoring communities. While [27] suggests the use of “canonical forms”, in which skeletons can easily be introduced, and to which equivalent code can be transformed, this work is limited by the number of forms identified. Similarly, [34] uses an analysis technique called program slicing to better inform refactorings to aid the introduction of concurrency in Erlang programs. This work does not use skeletons, however, instead relying upon Erlang’s concurrency primitives, restricting it to Erlang. In contrast to our work, most current research focuses in parallel refactoring on simple compile-time optimisations instead of source-to-source refactorings [24]. The approach presented in our paper therefore not only improves upon current methodologies by enabling their use on heterogeneous architectures, but also helps to introduce some automation to the previously-manual program shaping stage.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Although advances in structured parallel techniques greatly simplify the task of introducing the mechanics of parallelism, these techniques do not immediately fit every program. In this paper, we have introduced novel program shaping techniques and shown how they can be employed alongside the SKEL library, an Erlang implementation of several algorithmic skeletons, to restructure and introduce parallelism to an Erlang implementation of a n Evolutionary Multi-agent System, a real world use case (universal optimisation meta-heuristics). However, although this technique is describe in terms of Erlang, it is in fact completely general and can be applied to other languages, too.

Starting from an idiomatic Erlang implementation of the EMAS, where every agent has been implemented as individual lightweight Erlang process, we have shown that the efficiency of such system may be significantly improved, by applying program shaping refactorings to introduce algorithmic skeletons. The described effect was especially visible for Rastrigin function optimisation (where the fitness function had a very low, linear cost, so communication-related issues could be significantly improved). For LABS optimisation, the cost of the fitness function (approximately quadratic) resulted in achieving similar speedups for all the tested configurations. In the best case, we have achieved super-linear speedups over the original sequential algorithm of over 70× on a 64-core machine.

For future work, we intend to apply our approach to other use cases and to further evaluate its effectiveness. It would be interesting to apply it to the Erlang Dialyzer, for example, and to compare our techniques with those that have been applied manually. We also intend to expand our library of program shaping tech-

niques, incorporating static analysis techniques to further automate the process, at the same time reducing the burden on the programmer.

A REFACTORING THE MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM (FULL LISTINGS)

1.1 Stage 1

We start shaping `loop/4` by extracting functions from the list comprehensions that are assigned to `Tagged`, `Groups`, and `Migrants` using the *Extract Comprehension Function* refactoring. This gives the following definitions.

```
loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  TagFun =
    fun (Agent) ->
      {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                     SP,
                                     Cf),
       Agent}
    end,
  Tagged = lists:map(TagFun, Islands),

  GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,
  Groups = lists:map(GroupFun, Tagged),

  MigrantFun =
    fun ({Island, Nr}) ->
      seq_migrate(lists:keyfind(migration,
                                1, Island),
                  Nr)
    end,
  Migrants = lists:map(MigrantFun,
                       lists:zip(Groups,
                                 lists:seq(
                                   1,
                                   length(Groups)))),

  NewGroups = [[mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(
                 Activity,
                 mas_sequential,
                 SP,
                 Cf) || Activity <- I]
               || I <- Groups],

  WithMigrants = append(
    lists:flatten(Migrants),
    NewGroups),

  NewIslands =
    [mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
     || I <- WithMigrants],

  case os:tstamp() < Time of
  true ->
    loop(NewIslands, Time, SP, Cf);
  false ->
    NewIslands
  end.
```

1.2 Stage 2

To facilitate its eventual composition with `TagFun` and `GroupFun`, we inline the function `MigrantsFun` using the classical *Inline Method* refactoring.

```
loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  TagFun =
    fun (Agent) ->
      {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                     SP,
                                     Cf),
       Agent}
    end,
  Tagged = lists:map(TagFun, Islands),

  GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,
  Groups = lists:map(GroupFun, Tagged),

  MigrantFun =
    fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
      Destinations =
        [mas_topology:getDestination(From),
         Agent] || Agent <- Agents],
        mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
      (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent
    end,
  Migrants = lists:map(MigrantFun,
                      lists:zip(Groups,
                                lists:seq(
                                  1,
                                  length(Groups)))),

  NewGroups = [[mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(
                 Activity,
                 mas_sequential,
                 SP,
                 Cf) || Activity <- I]
               || I <- Groups],

  WithMigrants = append(
    lists:flatten(Migrants),
    NewGroups),

  NewIslands = [mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
                || I <- WithMigrants],

  case os:timestamp() < Time of
  true ->
    loop(NewIslands, Time, SP, Cf);
  false ->
    NewIslands
  end.
```

1.3 Stage 3

Since `MigrantsFun` can now be composed with `TagFun` and `GroupFun`, we compose these three functions using the *Compose Functions* refactoring.

```
loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  TagFun =
    fun (Agent) ->
      {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                     SP,
                                     Cf),
       Agent}
    end,

  GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,

  MigrantFun =
    fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
      Destinations =
        [[mas_topology:getDestination(From),
          Agent] || Agent <- Agents],
      mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
      (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent
    end,

  TGM = tgm(TagFun, GroupFun, MigrantFun),
  TGMs = lists:map(TGM, Islands),

  NewGroups = [[mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(
    Activity,
    mas_sequential,
    SP,
    Cf) || Activity <- I]
  || I <- TGMs],

  NewIslands = [mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
  || I <- NewGroups],

  case os:timestamp() < Time of
  true ->
    loop(NewIslands, Time, SP, Cf);
  false ->
    NewIslands
  end.
```

Here we note that the input to the list comprehension assigned to `NewGroups` has been changed according to the newly introduced composition. Similarly we also remove `WithMigrants` with the `Remove Statement` refactoring, which requires the input to the list comprehension assigned to `NewIslands` to be changed to `NewGroups`.

1.4 Stage 4

We next focus our attention on the list comprehensions assigned to `NewGroups` and `NewIslands` respectively, applying the *Extract Comprehension Function* refactoring to both.

```

loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  TagFun =
    fun (Agent) ->
      {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                     SP,
                                     Cf),
       Agent}
    end,

  GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,

  MigrantFun =
    fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
      Destinations =
        [{mas_topology:getDestination(From),
          Agent} || Agent <-Agents],
        mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
      (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent
    end,

  TGM = tgm(TagFun, GroupFun, MigrantFun),
  TGMs = lists:map(TGM, Islands),

  NewGroupsFunInnerFun =
    fun (Activity) ->
      mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(Activity,
                                   mas_sequential,
                                   SP,
                                   Cf)
    end,

  NewGroupsFun =
    fun (I) ->
      lists:map(NewGroupsFunInnerFun, I)
    end,
  NewGroups = lists:map(NewGroupsFun, TGMs),

  NewIslandsFun =
    fun (I) ->
      mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
    end,
  NewIslands = lists:map(NewIslandsFun, NewGroups),

  case os:timestamp() < Time of
    true ->
      loop(NewIslands, Time, SP, Cf);
    false ->
      NewIslands
  end.

```

1.5 Stage 5

Having shaped our existing functions into a suitable form for parallelisation, we now proceed to introduce the structures to pass to SKEL. We start with the map operation which applies TGM to each element in `Islands`, transforming it using the *Intro Func* refactoring to introduce a `func` skeleton. We apply the same refactoring to the `NewGroupsInnerFun` expression. Continuing this process, we next apply the *Intro Farm* refactoring over the `NewGroupsFun` expression.

```
loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  TagFun =
    fun (Agent) ->
      {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                     SP,
                                     Cf),
       Agent}
    end,

  GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,

  MigrantFun =
    fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
      Destinations =
        [{mas_topology:getDestination(From),
          Agent} || Agent <-Agents],
          mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
      (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent
    end,

  TGM = tgm(TagFun, GroupFun, MigrantFun),
  TGMs = {func, TGM},

  Work =
    {func,
     fun (Activity) ->
       mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(Activity,
                                    mas_farm,
                                    SP,
                                    Cf)
     end},

  Map = {farm, [Work], Cf#config.skel_workers},
  NewGroups = lists:map(NewGroupsFun, TGMs),

  Shuffle =
    fun (I) ->
      mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
    end,
  NewIslands = lists:map(Shuffle, NewGroups),

  case os:timestamp() < Time of
  true ->
    loop(NewIslands, Time, SP, Cf);
  false ->
    NewIslands
  end.
```

To aid readability we also rename `NewIslandsFun` to `Shuffle`.

1.6 Stage 6

We again apply the *Intro Func* refactoring, this time over the renamed `Shuffle` expression, completing all the skeletons that are required to introduce the `SKEL` invocation. We can then apply the *Intro Skel* refactoring over `NewIslands` and `NewGroups`.

```
loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  TagFun =
    fun (Agent) ->
      {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                     SP,
                                     Cf),
       Agent}
    end,

  GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,

  MigrantFun =
    fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
      Destinations =
        [{mas_topology:getDestination(From),
          Agent} || Agent <-Agents],
        mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
      (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent
    end,

  TGM = tgm(TagFun, GroupFun, MigrantFun),
  TGMs = {func, TGM},

  Work =
    {func,
     fun (Activity) ->
       mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(Activity,
                                    mas_farm,
                                    SP,
                                    Cf)
     end},
  Map = {farm, [Work], Cf#config.skel_workers},

  Shuffle =
    {func,
     fun (I) ->
       mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))
     end},

  Pipe = {pipe, [TGMs, Map, Shuffle]},
  NewIslands =
    [NewIsland ||
     {_, NewIsland} <- skel:do([Pipe], Islands)],

  case os:timestamp() < Time of
  true ->
    loop(NewIslands, Time, SP, Cf);
  false ->
    NewIslands
  end.
```

1.7 Stage 7

While `loop/4` is now parallel, the outer loop itself can also be folded into the SKEL invocation to improve efficiency. We do this by applying the *Intro Feedback Loop* refactoring over `loop/4` itself.

```
loop(Islands, Time, SP, Cf) ->
  EndTime =
    mas_misc_util:add_miliseconds(os:timestamp(), Time),

  TagFun =
    fun (Agent) ->
      {mas_misc_util:behaviour_proxy(Agent,
                                     SP,
                                     Cf), Agent}

    end,

  GroupFun = fun (I) -> mas_misc_util:group_by(I) end,

  MigrantFun =
    fun ({migration, Agents}, From) ->
      Destinations =
        [{mas_topology:getDestination(From),
          Agent} || Agent <-Agents],
      mas_misc_util:group_by(Destinations);
      (OtherAgent) -> OtherAgent

    end,

  TGM = tgm(TagFun, GroupFun, MigrantFun),
  TGMs = {func, TGM},

  Work = {func,
          fun (Activity) ->
            mas_misc_util:meeting_proxy(
              Activity,
              mas_farm,
              SP,
              Cf)

          end},

  Map = {farm, [Work], Cf#config.skel_workers},

  Shuffle = {func,
            fun (I) ->
              mas_misc_util:shuffle(lists:flatten(I))

            end},

  Pipe = {pipe, [TGMs, Map, Shuffle]},
  Constraint = fun (_) -> os:timestamp() < Time end,
  FinalIslands = skel:do([farm,
                          [{feedback, [Pipe], Constraint}],
                          Cf#config.skel_workers}],
                          [Islands]).
```

This completes the shaping and parallelisation process.

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